

Rare Adolescent Presentation of a Large Well-Differentiated Non-Functional Pancreatic Neuroendocrine Tumor

Sara Abadi ✉, Mohamed Tahiri, Lekhdim Wissam, Zineb Boukhal, Fatima Zahra El Rhaoussi, Fouad Haddad, Wafaa Hliwa, Ahmed Bellabah, Wafaa Badre

Gastroenterology Department, Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract

Pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (PNETs) are rare pancreatic neoplasms and are even more uncommon in adolescents. Large PNETs often manifest with mass effect or complications, yet they may occasionally present with minimal symptoms or even discovered incidentally. We report an exceptional case of a 17-year-old girl who presented with minimal epigastric pain and was found to have a large, well-defined 9-cm mass arising from the pancreatic head. Exploratory laparoscopy with biopsy confirmed a well-differentiated Grade I non-functional PNET. The lesion was considered unresectable, and the patient was referred for systemic therapy. This case is remarkable for the young age at presentation and the unusually large tumor size despite minimal symptoms, highlighting the importance of considering pancreatic tumors in the differential diagnosis of subtle abdominal symptoms in young patients.

Introduction

Pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (PNET) are tumors originating from neuroendocrine cells present in pancreas. According to the Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results (SEER) Program, the incidence of PNET is rising, reported in 2023 as 0.48 per 100,000 new cases per year [1]. The majority (between 50% and 85%) of PNET are nonfunctional [2]. Moreover, NF-PNET tend to present with more advanced disease and arise in the head of the pancreas [2]. Consequently, patients with NF-PNET have a significantly worse overall survival than their functioning counterparts ($p < .001$) [3], despite the rise of the five-year survival rate from 37% in 2000 to 58,9% in 2013 [4].

PNETs are classified as functional or non-functional. In this discussion, we will focus on the non-functional subtype. We present an exceptional case of a remarkable large size, non-functioning PNET in a teenage female.

Case Report

A 17-year-old girl presented with intermittent epigastric pain evolving for 1 month before admission.

She had no history of tuberculosis, diabetes, or any other major illness in past. Family history was not significant. The pain was non-radiating, not related to meals, and without associated symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, jaundice, diarrhea, hypoglycemic symptoms, or loss of appetite. The clinical picture developed while the patient's condition remained preserved.

On clinical examination, the patient was afebrile, and there was no icterus. Abdominal examination, reveals mild abdominal sensitivity without guarding or contracture, associated with palpable abdominal mass extending from the right flank to the epigastrium, fixed in relation to the deep plane, poorly defined, measuring 8cm. Per rectal examination were insignificant.

On admission, an abdominal CT scan was requested, which showed a large tumor process affecting the head of the pancreas, oval in shape, well defined, with regular contours, heterodense, containing a few spontaneously hyperdense areas and hypodense areas (probably necrosis) without calcification within it. This mass enhances heterogeneously after contrast

More Information

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injection, measuring 94 x 67.8 cm and extending over 72.7 cm.

Figure 1-2: Intraoperative Laparoscopic Image Demonstrating Biopsy of a Pancreatic Head Mass. The Lesion Appears Solid-Cystic and Well-Encapsulated

Endoscopic ultrasound (EUS) revealed the presence of an encapsulated exophytic mass measuring 8 cm in diameter, in contact with the head of the pancreas with a separating margin. The mass was surrounded with major collateral circulation precluding biopsy.

An abdominal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scan revealed the presence of a large retroperitoneal tissue mass in the pancreaticoduodenal space, the epicenter of which appears to be at the expense of the pancreatic uncus, as evidenced by the spur sign with the head of the pancreas and the absence of visualization of the uncus. It is described as having a T2 hypersignal relative to the pancreas, a T1 hyposignal, peripheral diffusion restriction, intense enhancement in the arterial phase, delimiting an irregular central necrotic area. It measures 90.7x72.2mm and extends over 81mm.

This mass has the following characteristics:

- Posterior: It comes into contact with and pushes back the right kidney, with loss of the separating border in places, It pushes back the right renal pedicle and the left renal vein, It laminates and pushes back the inferior vena cava inward and It comes into contact with the lumbar head of the psoas-iliac muscle, with loss of the separating border in places.
- Anteriorly: It appears to come into contact with the anterior abdominal wall without any clear signs of invasion.

- Medially: It comes into contact with the superior mesenteric vein over a circumference of 180°, which remains permeable. Further down, it comes into contact with the aorta, with preservation of the fatty separation border. The separating border with the superior mesenteric artery, the celiac trunk, and the hepatic artery is preserved.
- Outward: It comes into close contact with the right hepatic lobe and the gallbladder, with no clear signs of detectable invasion.
- Below: it comes into contact with the ascending colon with loss of the fatty border separating them.
- Above and outside: It comes into close contact with and pushes back the duodenum with loss of the separating border.
- No infiltration of the peripancreatic fat.
- Liver of normal size, with regular contours, no detectable focal lesions and no detectable abdominal lymphadenopathy

In light of the radiological examination data (abdominal CT scan and MRI) showing that the mass was unresectable, the decision was made to perform exploratory laparoscopy with biopsy of the mass.

Figure 3-4: Abdominal MRI Demonstrating a Large, Well-Defined Mass Centered in the Pancreatic Head

An exploratory laparoscopy was performed. The examination found no intraperitoneal effusion, nor any peritoneal or hepatic nodules. A 2 cm adenopathy of the gastrocolic ligament was identified and resected after vascular control with bipolar forceps; The

extemporaneous examination concluded that the lymph node pulp was free of tumor proliferation. The procedure involved colo-epiploic detachment with lowering of the right colic angle, revealing a solid-cystic mass of the head of the pancreas measuring approximately 8 cm, with supra- and submesocolic development. A tru-cut biopsy was performed with satisfactory hemostasis. The histological examination concerned five biopsy fragments corresponding to fibrous tissue with tumor proliferation arranged in rows, clusters, and sometimes diffuse. The cells are small, with anisokaryotic nuclei and salt-and-pepper chromatin, with rare mitotic figures (< 2 mitoses/10CFG). An immunohistochemical study was performed and showed Based on histopathology and immunohistochemistry the positivity for anti-CD56 and anti-Chromogranin A antibodies, with an estimated Ki67 proliferation index of 2%. The diagnosis of malignant PNET (Grade 1) was made.

Due to the presence of advanced disease the patient was considered ineligible for surgical treatment. The patient was discharged on the 5th post-operative day and she was then referred to the oncology department for neoadjuvant systemic therapy with lanreotide (Somatuline).

Discussion

Although pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (PNETs) can manifest at any age, non-functional forms (NF-PNETs) are mostly diagnosed between the fourth and sixth decades of life, with a median age at presentation of around 59–61 years in large SEER-based cohorts [4]. The case we present is remarkable, since our patient was a 17-year-old adolescent girl, which makes the age highly unusual. Pediatric cases remain exceptional; in a French national series of 15 patients aged 7 to 17 years, the median age at diagnosis was 14 years, with most localized disease [3]. Similarly, the German MET study, which included 28 patients, found a median diagnostic age of 14.7 years [5].

The majority, 90%, of NF-PNETs are sporadic, while 10% are associated with hereditary syndromes. Among these, we find that 75% of patients with multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1 (MEN1) will develop non-functional PNETs. The Von Hippel–Lindau (VHL) disease carries also a high risk of PNETs, with a prevalence reaching 20% [6].

NF-PNETs are biologically inactive or secrete peptides and hormones that do not lead to clinical syndromes, such as pancreatic polypeptide, chromogranin A, ghrelin, calcitonin, or neurotensin (6). They often remain asymptomatic until they produce symptoms related to tumor size or mass effect, such as abdominal pain [7]. Compared with functioning PNETs, NF-PNETs are typically diagnosed at more advanced stages, with higher T-stage, nodal involvement, or distant metastases, resulting in poorer overall survival [1]. Our

patient presented with a large pancreatic mass exceeding 8 cm revealed by intermittent epigastric pain or metastases.

Cross-sectional imaging is essential for diagnostic workup. Contrast-enhanced (CT) remains the first-line modality given its sensitivity, specificity, and availability. PNETs generally appear as well-circumscribed, hypervascular masses with heterogeneous enhancement (8). Magnetic resonance imaging MRI offers the advantage of avoiding repeated radiation exposure and better sensitivity for small pancreatic lesions and liver metastases and it represents a valuable alternative, particularly in younger patients. PNETs appear hypointense on T1-weighted images and hyperintense on T2-weighted images [9]. Endoscopic ultrasound (EUS) plays also a main role, especially for getting cytological or histological samples by fine needle aspiration [10]. Actually, somatostatin receptor PET/CT (68Ga-DOTATATE or similar tracers) is considered now the most sensitive technique for staging, detecting metastases, and characterizing the primary lesion, according to the current recommendations by the North American Neuroendocrine Tumor Society [11]. In our case, MRI and EUS was sufficient for diagnosis and staging, and PET was not performed because the tumor was characterized as a large, well-vascularized pancreatic mass without evidence of distant metastases.

Histological confirmation remains essential. Diagnosis is based on characteristic neuroendocrine architecture (nested, trabecular, or solid patterns) and immunohistochemical positivity for markers such as synaptophysin and chromogranin A [7]. Grading is based on proliferative activity, judged by mitotic figures (expressed as mitoses/2 mm²) and expression of the Ki-67 antigen (as percentage of all tumor cells) [12]. According to WHO 2019, tumors are classified as: Grade 1 (well-differentiated, mitotic count $< 2/2$ mm² and Ki-67 $< 3\%$), Grade 2 (well-differentiated, mitotic count 2–20/2 mm² or Ki-67 3–20%), and Grade 3 (well-differentiated, mitotic count $> 20/2$ mm² or Ki-67 $> 20\%$) [13]. In our case, the tumor was Grade 1 and it showed strong chromogranin expression, with an estimated Ki67 proliferation index of 2%.

The management of a PNET depends on tumor location, grade, and stage. Therapeutic options can extend from active surveillance especially for small, asymptomatic lesions without nodal involvement, to surgical resection for localized disease, and systemic therapy for unresectable tumors. Surgical resection remains the treatment of choice for localized PNETs, with pancreatoduodenectomy for head lesions and distal pancreatectomy (with or without splenectomy) for tumors in the body and tail [6]. Radical resection of

pancreatic tumors has a particularly favorable long-term outcomes in children and adolescents [8].

In unresectable NF-PNETs, treatment choice is influenced by tumor burden and biological aggressiveness. Somatostatin analogs such as octreotide or lanreotide are the first-line treatment agents for patients with relatively small tumor burden and slow disease progression, while cytotoxic chemotherapy (such as streptozotocin, 5-fluorouracil or doxorubicin) would be selected in cases of bulky or rapidly progressive tumors. Molecular-targeted agents, including everolimus and sunitinib, are options intermediate tumor volume and/or an intermediate growth rate [14].

In our patient, the tumor was very large, locally advanced, and infiltrating adjacent structures, making it unresectable. A multidisciplinary tumor board therefore decided to start a neoadjuvant systemic therapy with lanreotide (Somatuline).

Surveillance is essential in this context. Following ENETS recommendations, imaging should be scheduled every 3–6 months during the first two years. If stability is maintained beyond this period, the interval will be extended to 6–12 months. Given the young age of our patient, MRI with hepatocyte-specific contrast will be chosen to avoid repeated radiation exposure and improve detection of small liver lesions. Chromogranin A can be monitored throughout follow-up, with the although isolated elevations should not prompt immediate therapy modification in the absence of radiological evidence of disease progression [10]. In our case, follow-up will rely on MRI every 3–6 months during the first two years, given the patient's young age.

Conclusion

Non-functional pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors are particularly rare in adolescents and may remain clinically asymptomatic until they reach a considerable size. This case illustrates that even well-differentiated, Grade I tumors can present as large, locally advanced masses with minimal symptoms. Early diagnosis recognition is essential for timely management and improved outcomes.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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